

ARDC Data Retention Project: Metadata Relating to Criteria

1.1 Metadata relating to Eligibility Criteria

Occ 1 = Required not repeatable

Occ1-n = Required repeatable

Metadata ID	occ	Metadata Concept	DataCite Schema ID	Accepted value types	Comments/Guidance
E01	1	Collection capacity	13 Size	Terabyte-TB	ARDC requires volume capacity in terabytes (1TB = 10 ¹² bytes)
E02	1-n	Local Collection ID	11 AlternateIdentifier	local ID	User defined local ID
E03	1-n	Applicable research disciplines	6 Subject	Fields of research (FoR) codes.	2-, 4- or 6-character codes
E04	1	Title	3 Title	Free text	Brief title used to describe the data collection
E05	1	Description	17 Description	Free text	Contextual abstract description of the collection
E06	1-n	Data Controller/s	4 Publisher	Research Organisation Registration (ROR)	The role of 'Publisher' is given prominence in data citation and will generally represent a primary role with rights over data collections or delegated authority from rights holders. Partners may wish to include the optional term 'contributor' (DataCite schema ID7) for other types of related roles, see V03 below.

1.2 Metadata relating to Value Criteria

Occ 1 = Required not repeatable

Occ1-n = Required repeatable

Metadata ID	Occ	Metadata Concept	DataCite Schema ID	Accepted value types	Comments/Guidance
V01	1	Collection ID	1 Identifier	Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	Specifically, a DataCite DOI
V02	1	Actionable Digital Location	12 RelatedIdentifier	URL or URI to registry entry	Can be a local data repository registry or catalogue. Partners may wish to make use of Research Data Australia
V03	1-n	Owner/s (Contributors)	2 Creator (7 Contributor)	ORCID for individuals or ROR for institutions.	Creator roles identify rights holders and possess important legal status. Contributor is provided as an optional term that can be used for interests other than the mandatory terms of Publisher and Owner/s, e.g. a data repository or data storage service.
V04	1-n	Merit	19 FundingReference 12 RelatedIdentifier	Grant number (for 19) Citation 'IsCitedBy' or IsSupplementTo or isReferencedby etc (for 12)	
V05	1	License	16 Rights	Appropriate and formal licenses or waiver notices	ARDC recommends use of Creative Commons Licenses and waiver notices.
V06	1	Collection type	10 ResourceType	Controlled list values	e.g., dataset
V07	1	Publication Year	5 Publication year	YYYY	Generally taken to be when collection was made available or the year it was registered in DataCite.